

High-Precision Algebraic Relations for the Magnetic Moments of Light Nuclei

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Abstract

We studied the nuclear magnetic moments of ten light nuclei, which are deuteron, tritium, helium-3, lithium-6, lithium-7, beryllium-9, boron-10, boron-11, proton and neutron. We found that there are some previously unknown high-precision algebraic relations between their nuclear magnetic moments, which make the nuclear magnetic moments of different nuclei bind together in a very simple way. This relation is closely related to the nuclear cluster model, yet there are no complex corrections associated with it. This finding in this paper proposes a possible new model and insights for the study of nuclear magnetic moments.

Keywords: Light nuclei, nuclear magnetic moments, algebraic relations, spin g-factor, high-precision, nucleon

Introduction

In the cluster model of nuclei^[2], when calculating the nuclear magnetic moment of an atomic nucleus, the nuclear magnetic moment of several smaller nuclei is usually used as an input parameter. This model shows that there is a relationship between the nuclear magnetic moments of different nuclei^[2]. However, the cluster model of atomic nuclei cannot give an accurate algebraic relationship between them^[1], and the relationship between their nuclear magnetic moments is linked by complex formulas^{[2][3][11]}, which not only does not have high calculation accuracy, but also introduces multiple corrections^{[3][12]}. And Our formulas can avoid these shortcomings and directly give the concise relationship between them, which makes it easy to understand the mutual change and restriction relationship between nuclear magnetic moments.

Since the nuclear magnetic moments of various nuclei are involved in this paper, in order to facilitate the understanding of the relationship we give about them, we need to give a unified description of their symbols. See Table 1.

Nucleus	Nuclear magnetic moment symbol	Experimental value (μ/μ_N)	Reference
0 n 1 (n)	$g_I^{(n)}$	-1.91304276(45)	[4]
1 H 1 (p)	$g_I^{(p)}$	2.79284734463(82)	[4]
1 H 2 (D)	$g_I^{(D)}$	0.8574382338(26)	[6]
1 H 3 (T)	$g_I^{(T)}$	2.9789624650(59)	[6]
2 He 3	$g_I^{(He3)}$	-2.1276253498(15)	[5]
3 Li 6	$g_I^{(Li6)}$	0.82204463(37)	[8]
3 Li 7	$g_I^{(Li7)}$	3.25641619(57)	[8]
4 Be 9	$g_I^{(Be9)}$	-1.17743163444(65)	[9]
5 B 10	$g_I^{(B10)}$	1.8004636(8)	[7]
5 B 11	$g_I^{(B11)}$	2.6883781(11)	[7]

Table 1: Symbols and values of nuclear magnetic moments

Since we need to use some other physical quantities when we explore the relationship between the nuclear magnetic moments of each nucleus, here we also give a unified description of them. See Table 2.

Physical quantitie	Symbol	Experimental value	Reference
Proton spin g-factor	g_p	5.5856946893(16)	[4]
Neutron spin g-factor	g_n	-3.82608552(90)	[4]
Electron spin g-factor	g_e	$-2 \times 1.00115965218046(18)$	[4]
Muon spin g-factor	g_μ	$-2 \times 1.001165920715(145)$	[10]
The fine structure constant	α	0.0072973525643(11)	[4]

Table 2: Symbols and values of physical quantities

We found a total of 10 magnetic moment relationships of light nuclei, which are related to each other in various ways, and each relationship is different. Here is their formula. In particular, the nuclear magnetic moment in this article has a plus or minus sign.

1. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for D, T, He3, n

$$\left(\frac{g_e - g_n}{\sqrt{\pi}}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \cdot \frac{g_\mu}{g_e} = \frac{g_I^{(D)}}{g_I^{(T)} + g_I^{(He3)}} \quad (1)$$

Where, π is the pi.

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (1) is: 1.0071665110.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (1) is: 1.0071665131.

2. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for He3, Li7, Be9, p

$$\frac{g_I^{(p)} - g_I^{(Li7)}/s_{Li7}}{g_I^{(p)}} \cdot \frac{g_\mu}{g_e} \cdot \frac{45}{4} = g_I^{(He3)} \cdot g_I^{(Be9)} \quad (2)$$

Where, $s_{Li7} = 3/2$, It is the nuclear spin quantum number of Li7^[14].

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (2) is: 2.505133344.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (2) is: 2.505133393.

3. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for He3, Li6, Li7

$$-\left(g_I^{(Li6)} + g_I^{(He3)}\right) \cdot 10 \cdot \frac{g_\mu}{g_e} = g_I^{(Li7)} \cdot g_e^2 \quad (3)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (3) is: 13.055889.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (3) is: 13.055893.

4. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for D, Be9, B10, B11, n

$$\left[\frac{g_I^{(B10)} + g_I^{(Be9)}}{g_I^{(B10)}} \cdot \frac{g_I^{(B11)}}{g_I^{(B11)} - g_I^{(B10)}} \cdot \frac{3}{\pi} \right]^4 = g_I^{(n)} \cdot \frac{g_\mu}{g_e} \cdot \frac{g_I^{(D)} - g_I^{(B10)}}{g_I^{(B10)}} \quad (4)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (4) is: 1.00199664.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (4) is: 1.00199701.

5. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for D, Li6, Be9, n

$$\frac{g_n^2}{-\left(g_n + g_I^{(Li6)}\right)} \cdot \frac{g_I^{(D)}}{\left(g_I^{(Be9)}\right)^2} = \frac{3g_e^4}{16} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 + \alpha/2\pi}{-g_e/2}} \quad (5)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (5) is: 3.01394242.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (5) is: 3.01394270.

6. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for T, He3, Li7, Be9, n, p

$$\frac{-3}{g_I^{(\text{Li7})} + g_I^{(\text{He3})}} \cdot \frac{g_I^{(p)} + g_I^{(n)}}{g_I^{(\text{T})}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g_e}{g_e^{(\text{He3})}}} = \frac{g_I^{(\text{Be9})}}{s_{\text{Be9}}} \quad (6)$$

Where, $g_e^{(\text{He3})} = -2.00217741579(34)$. It is the experimental measurement of the g-factor of the bound electron in the ground state of $^3\text{He}^+$ ion^[5]; $s_{\text{Be9}} = 3/2$. It is the nuclear spin quantum number of Be9^[14].

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (6) is: -0.78495427.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (6) is: -0.78495442296(42).

7. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for T, He3, Li7, n, p

$$3\left(g_I^{(\text{Li7})} + g_I^{(\text{He3})}\right) \cdot \frac{g_I^{(p)} + g_I^{(n)}}{g_I^{(\text{T})}} = -\left(\frac{g_e}{2}\right)^{\frac{1}{9}} \quad (7)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (7) is: 1.000128771.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (7) is: 1.000128783.

8. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for He3, Li6, n, p

$$\frac{-g_I^{(\text{He3})}}{3g_I^{(\text{Li6})} + g_I^{(\text{He3})}} \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} = \frac{3g_e + g_p}{9} \cdot \frac{g_\mu}{g_e} \cdot g_p g_n \quad (8)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (8) is: 1.00033545.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (8) is: 1.00033537.

9. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for D, T, He3, Li7, n, p

$$\frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{g_I^{(\text{Li7})} + g_I^{(\text{He3})} + g_I^{(\text{D})}}{g_I^{(\text{T})}} = \left[\frac{-g_n}{g_p + g_e} \cdot \frac{g_I^{(p)}}{g_I^{(\text{T})}} \right]^{\frac{1}{8}} \quad (9)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (9) is: 1.000127946.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (9) is; 1.000127955.

10. Nuclear magnetic moment relation for Li6, Be9, B11

$$-\frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(g_I^{(\text{Be9})}\right)^3 \cdot g_I^{(\text{Li6})} \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{g_e g_\mu}{1 + \alpha/2\pi}\right)^3} = g_I^{(\text{B11})} \quad (10)$$

The calculated value on the left side of Equation (10) is: 2.68837864.

The calculated value on the right side of Equation (10) is: 2.6883781(11).

We give the above 10 formulas, and their calculation results are in good agreement within the accuracy range. This precise and concise algebraic relationship of nuclear magnetic moments may be a coincidence. Although we have no derivation process, it may also be their true relationship. These relations have changed people's inherent cognition of nuclear magnetic moment calculation, suggesting that there are unknown simple rules between different light nuclear magnetic moments to constrain each other. In any case, from the above relationships, it can be seen that the cluster model of the nucleus has a great influence on the nuclear magnetic moment. In addition, these relations in this paper provide a new insight for understanding the structure of nuclei and the interaction between them. In the future, with the improvement of experimental accuracy^[13], these relations in this paper may be further improved.

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